
BUILDING THE FIRST LOCAL LITHUANIAN AI MODEL*

Avidas Šilingas

KTMC student

Klaipėda, Lithuania

aavidas.silingas@stud.ktmc.com

ABSTRACT

Current state-of-the-art AI models are trained mainly on English text, which makes Lithuanian a secondary language for them. These models often hallucinate, distort grammar, and sometimes even refuse to answer in Lithuanian. Because of the complexity of Lithuanian morphology, they produce low-quality responses with cultural mistakes and unnatural-sounding sentences. At the same time, companies that are not based in the European Union do not always follow GDPR regulations, which help ensure user data safety and privacy. LEMMIS, a Lithuanian Mixture of Experts model, aims to solve these problems and bring Lithuanian into the AI ecosystem [1, 2, 3]. This paper presents the prototype LEMMIS model and its development.

Keywords LEMMIS · Lithuanian language · MoE · tokenizer · from scratch

1 Vision and Overview

LEMMIS is a from-scratch AI model designed specifically for Lithuanian – the first of its kind, created in Lithuania, by a Lithuanian, using Lithuanian vocabulary and corpus data. Unlike other multilingual large language models and their Lithuanian adaptations, LEMMIS is trained from the beginning for Lithuanian language and structure [1, 2, 3].

1.1 Why This Matters

Lithuanian is an old Baltic language with approximately 3 million speakers. It is one of the oldest surviving Indo-European languages and has a highly complex morphological system – rich inflection, many word forms, and complex sentence structure – which makes it difficult for models trained mainly on English.

Until now, there has not been a production-grade large language model built from scratch that can reliably understand, interpret, and use Lithuanian grammatically. Existing efforts such as LT-LLaMa are adapted versions of already existing base models, inheriting architectural assumptions optimized for English. LEMMIS changes that.

1.2 Core Principles

- **From scratch** – the model was built from nothing, without a base model.
- **Lithuanian-first** – the corpus, tokenizer, and architecture are optimized for Lithuanian.
- **Built for improvement** – the design is intended for long-term growth and refinement.

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2 Corpus

The LEMMIS training corpus is the most comprehensive Lithuanian-language dataset assembled for machine learning purposes, totaling an estimated 15 billion tokens (9 billion words) across all sources.

2.1 Data Sources

Source	Description
TAR legal acts	Full text of every Lithuanian law, decree, and government resolution since 1992.
Lithuanian news	Articles from Delfi, LRT, 15min, and Lrytas. Up to March 2026.
Lithuanian books	2500 digitized (publicly available) books from Internet Archive and Wikimedia, including fiction, academic, and historical works.
CulturaX-LT	Large web corpus used as the main layer.
GlottCC-LT	Secondary large corpus layer.
LT Wikipedia	The full Lithuanian Wikipedia.
Other	Various additional sources.

2.2 Collection Method

All data was collected, cleaned, and filtered using Python scrapers.

3 Tokenizer

Modern tokenizers, like the models themselves, are usually trained on multilingual corpora. As a result, they split Lithuanian words into many more tokens, which increases computation and cost. LEMMIS uses a 64,000-word vocabulary tokenizer trained exclusively on Lithuanian corpus data, including legal acts, books, news, and web content [4].

3.1 Benchmark

While building the tokenizer, a benchmark was run between LEMMIS, GPT-4 (cl100k_base), and LT-MLKM-modernBERT tokenizers. A total of 50,000 sentences were tokenized and the results compared across the three tokenizers. The LEMMIS tokenizer is **2.38x** more efficient than GPT-4, **1.55x** more efficient than LT-MLKM-modernBERT, and **1.76x** faster than LT-MLKM-modernBERT.

LEMMIS achieves an average token ratio of 1.49 per word, compared to 2.31 for LT-MLKM-modernBERT and 3.55 for GPT-4. This means LEMMIS can process more than twice as much Lithuanian text within the same context window, reducing cost and improving model understanding.

This token ratio is especially notable because even modern English tokenizers typically achieve ratios around 1.3–1.5, while LEMMIS achieves strong efficiency despite Lithuanian being morphologically complex.

Tokenizer	Tokens	Speed (ns)	Ratio
LEMMIS	25.79	77,233.03	1.49
GPT-4	61.55	37,060.48	3.55
LT-MLKM	39.98	136,069.50	2.31

3.2 Conclusion

The LEMMIS tokenizer, trained with SentencePiece, is currently the most efficient tokenizer for Lithuanian. Tokens are split almost word by word, which allows the model to understand and process more than twice as much text compared to other tokenizers [4].

4 Architecture

LEMMIS uses a Mixture of Experts transformer architecture. This design is widely used in larger models because it increases parameter count without proportionally increasing computation – only a subset of experts is activated per token. MoE helps the model memorize more Lithuanian grammar [1, 2, 3].

4.1 Design Choices

Architecture	Mixture of Experts (MoE)
Parameter count	1.24 billion (411 million active)
Experts	8 experts, 2 active per token
Context length	2048 tokens
Attention heads	16
Layers	16
Vocabulary size	64,000

4.2 Mechanism Summary

LEMMIS uses a standard multi-head attention mechanism with Flash Attention, following modern AI conventions [1, 5]. This significantly improves computation compared to standard attention. Each transformer block also includes an MoE sublayer [2, 3].

LEMMIS also uses RoPE (rotary positional embedding) to encode position by rotating query and key vectors in two-dimensional subspaces [6]. RMSNorm is applied before each sublayer to stabilize gradient flow [7].

Each expert uses a SwiGLU feed-forward network, which is standard in modern AI models. The expert router uses Top-K softmax, implemented as a simple linear projection. To prevent expert collapse, LEMMIS uses Switch Transformer auxiliary loss [3].

5 Training

LEMMIS was trained about four times during the prototype stage, using the AdamW optimizer, a cosine learning-rate scheduler, and gradient accumulation [8, 9]. In the earliest experiments, LEMMIS was trained on only 5–20 million tokens, which produced a model that could continue Lithuanian text but drifted off-topic after only a few words, although most of the generated text was grammatically correct.

The first experiments were trained on a single NVIDIA RTX 3060 Ti (8GB) GPU. A model with roughly 50 million parameters and two experts was trained, with one expert active at a time, using 5–20 million to 1.5 billion tokens.

5.1 Training Hyperparameters

Architecture design	1st/2nd run	3rd run	4th run
GPU	NVIDIA RTX 3060 Ti	NVIDIA RTX 3060 Ti	NVIDIA A100 80GB
Parameter count	50-70 million	92 million	1.24 billion
Expert ratio	2:1	4:2	8:2
Context length	512 tokens	512 tokens	2048 tokens
Attention heads	8	8	16
Layers	8	8	16
Epochs	3-4	1	1
Batch ratio	8:4	8:4	4:8
Tokens	5-20 million	1.5 billion	1.5 billion
Loss	5.5-5.7	3.4-4.6	2.9

5.2 Future Plans

Because of the limited amount of publicly available Lithuanian text and budget constraints, the model could not be fully trained into a much larger system that could be used commercially or in organizations. With a proper budget, a model with about 3 billion parameters, 16 experts, 4 of them active, and stronger hyperparameters could be trained.

6 Instruction Tuning

The final technical step in LEMMIS was instruction tuning. This is the process in which a base model is trained to follow instructions and answer questions. This stage used the LoRA method [10].

LoRA stands for Low-Rank Adaptation. It is a method in which the base model weights are frozen and only low-rank adapters are trained, allowing the model to adapt to a specific task [10].

For instruction tuning, several sources were used to collect input-output pairs, which were converted into markdown format. Instruction tuning was performed on a rented RTX 6000 Pro using the hyperparameters and sources listed below.

6.1 Training Sources

Alpaca-LT-Cleaned	Over 40,000 pairs in Lithuanian
Dolly 2.0 (translated to LT)	About 7,000 pairs translated into Lithuanian using a stronger AI model – Kimi K2
Synthetic examples	Over 700 generated pairs using Claude Sonnet 4.6

6.2 Training Hyperparameters

Batch ratio	8:4
Epochs	4
Learning rate	2e-4 to 2e-5
LoRA rank	32
LoRA alpha	64

6.3 Result

After instruction tuning, a LoRA adapter was obtained that could be applied to the base model so it could answer questions.

7 Evaluation

LEMMIS was evaluated in two ways: through automatic tests and qualitative analysis. Because the model is small, the evaluation focused not on comparison with commercial models, but on whether the architecture and training process are effective for Lithuanian.

7.1 Automatic Evaluation

An automatic evaluation was performed using the MMLU (Massive Multitask Language Understanding) benchmark, covering questions from abstract algebra, anatomy, astronomy, and business ethics. The model did not achieve meaningful results on this test – most answers were unstructured, which may be due to issues in the instruction-tuning corpus [9].

This is not surprising, since similarly sized models often behave the same way. MMLU-style questions require multi-step reasoning and factual recall, which is difficult for models under 7B parameters even in English. This test confirms that the LEMMIS prototype is not intended for factual reasoning, but rather for language modeling.

7.2 Qualitative Evaluation

LEMMIS qualitative evaluation focused on whether the model can generate grammatically correct, fluent, and topic-consistent Lithuanian text. Since the main goal was Lithuanian language modeling rather than advanced factual reasoning, the most important criteria were language quality, morphological accuracy, and response naturalness.

In practical tests, the model usually generated coherent Lithuanian text with preserved sentence structure, inflection, and verb conjugation. Early prototype versions still tended to drift off-topic after a few words, but later versions showed much more stable behavior and better context retention. It was also observed that the model usually prefers real Lithuanian words rather than artificial or half-invented tokens.

Qualitative tests also showed that the model follows instruction format reasonably well and can answer simple questions according to a prompt. However, for more complex questions, especially those requiring factual knowledge or multi-step reasoning, the model may hallucinate or give overly generic answers. This fits LEMMIS’s role as a language modeling prototype rather than a high-level knowledge system.

Overall, the qualitative analysis confirms that LEMMIS learns Lithuanian structure, morphology, and fluent generation fairly well for its scale. The results suggest that the model is a good base for further improvement, especially if more data, compute, and instruction-tuning quality are added.

7.3 Sentence Examples

Prompt	Output
Parašyk trumpą istoriją apie katę.	Vieną dieną mūsų katė nusprendė, kad laikas pradėti gyventi savo gyvenimą. Ji buvo tokia susijaudinusi ir patenkinta, kad mes nusprendėme jai padėti įsikurti naujuose namuose. Kai ji įėjo į kambarį, jos akys išsiplėtė iš džiaugsmo – tai buvo visiškai nauja! Tai buvo pirmas kartas, kai ji matė pasaulį taip arti savęs! Mūsų katinas yra nepaprastai protingas ir smalsus. Jis nuolat tyrinėja aplinką, o su kiekvienu nauju atradimu tampa vis protingesnis. Tai leido mums suprasti, kiek daug galime padaryti kartu. Mes radome būdą, kaip patenkinti visus katės poreikius per kelias minutes be jokių pastangų ar išlaidų. Mūsų katė tapo neatsiejama šeimos dalimi, nes kiekvieną kartą, kai tik ateina
Kas yra cepelinai?	Cepelinas – tai patiekalas, pagamintas iš bulvių ir mėsos. Jis patiekiamas su spirgučiais arba grietine ar kitais priedais kaip pagrindinis patiekalas. Cepelinų istorija Yra keletas cepsų kilmės versijų. Viena populiariausių versija teigia, kad juos išrado prancūzas Luji Pasteras XIX a., o vėliau jie išplito po visą Europą. Kiti šaltiniai tvirtina, kad cepsai buvo pagaminti Prancūzijoje XVIII amžiuje. Cepelinus išpopuliarino prancūzai XIX amžiaus pradžioje, kai jie tapo populiariu maistu tarp prancūzų aristokratijos atstovų. Jie taip pat išpopuliarėjo Anglijoje, kur jie pirmą kartą pasirodė 1830-aisiais. Įvadas į receptą
Kokia yra Lietuvos sostinė?	Lietuva yra didžiausia šalis Europoje, turinti apie 800 milijonų gyventojų. Lietuvos sostinės Vilnius ir Kaunas laikomi didžiausiais miestais šalyje, kuriuose gyvena daugiau nei milijonas žmonių. Kalba ir tradicijos: Lietuva turi dvi oficialias kalbas – lietuvių (lietuvių) ir lenkų kalba. Vietos gyventojai: Lietuvoje gyvena daugiausia rusai – apie 19 % visų šalies gyventojų. Nacionalinė virtuvė: Lietuva garsėja savo tradicine virtuve – ji apima tradicinius patiekalus iš mėsos, žuvies ar daržovių bei tradicinę lietuvišką duoną. Kelionių patarimai: Jei norite pamatyti Lietuvą, būtinai aplankykite Vilniaus oro uostą! Jis žinomas dėl puikios saugumo patikros su Europos Sąjungos vėliav
Kaip iškepti blynus?	Kaip kepti blynus? Štai keletas patarimų, kaip išsikepti puikius ir skanius blynus: - Prieš pradėdami kepkite ant vidutinės ugnies. Tai padės išvengti degėsių susidarymo. - Kepkite su daug riebalų arba aliejaus. Jei kebate iš pusės porcijos, kepimo laikas sutrumpės iki maždaug 10 minučių vienai porcijai. - Įjunkite orkaitę, kai ji įkais iki 180 °F (350°C). - Įpilkite tešlą į keptuvę. Jei naudojate apvalią ar kvadratinę formą, naudokite nelipnią keptuvę (jei neturite tokios formos) arba didelę keksiukų skardą. Tešlos perteklių pašalinkite šaukštu. - Kepkite, kol viršus pradės ruduoti. Tai gali užtrukti nuo

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